

Beyond Stargazing: The Sustainable Astrotourism Framework

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Abstract:

Cyprus is an island that relies heavily on the 'sun and sea' tourism model. This creates unsustainable seasonality within the tourism industry. Little has been done in Cyprus to diversify the tourism market despite having much more to offer. The island is home to some of the darkest, and clearest, night skies in Europe, excellent weather conditions, and an optimal geographic location. This makes Cyprus ideal for astronomical observations and opens the door to a unique form of tourism, Astrotourism. Realising this gap, a specialised team came together with the objective of developing a series of Astrotourism activities, in a sustainable manner. To do this, the authors, as sustainability experts, created a framework to ensure the Astrotourism activities are implemented in a way that would produce environmental, economic, social, and cultural benefits. The developed sustainability framework guides activity organisers towards making sustainable choices related to location, set-up, equipment, resource consumption, and waste management. The Astrotourism sustainability framework was applied and tested over three pilots, spanning three seasons and three locations on the island of Cyprus, and was evaluated through feedback questionnaires and on-site observations. This paper presents the sustainability framework and the results from the three pilot tests in Cyprus.

Astrotourism (Integrated/0918/0038) is co-funded by the ERDF and the Republic of Cyprus through the RIF.

Keywords: tourism diversification, management, sustainability, Cyprus